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Адрес редакции:

Республика Узбекистан, 200100, г.
Бухара, ул. Гиждуванская, 23.

Телефон (99865) 223-00-50

Факс (99866) 223-00-50

Сайт <https://bsmi.uz/journals/fundamental-ya-klinik-tibbiyot-ahborotnomasi/>

e-mail baymuradovravshan@gmail.com

О журнале

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THE IMPORTANCE OF SERUM PEPSINOGEN LEVEL IN THE STUDY OF THE MORPHOFUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE STOMACH WALL**Yusupova N.A., Mannonova N.U., Sanaeva P., Kurbanova Sh.B.**

Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Resume. Morphological assessment of the gastric mucosa is extremely labor-intensive due to the need for endoscopy, biopsy, and histological examination. In addition, even several biopsies do not provide a clear picture due to the focal, uneven nature of gastritis. In recent decades, determination of the serum concentration of pepsinogens I and II has been used for non-invasive assessment of the state of the gastric mucosa. The article provides information on the importance of pepsinogens in assessing the condition of the stomach wall and their changes in various Genesis diseases.

Key words: enzyme immunoassay, pepsinogen 1 (PGI), pepsinogen 2 (PGII), blood serum, stomach, ELIS

ОШҚОЗОН ДЕВОРИНИНГ МОРФОФУНКЦИОНАЛ ҲОЛАТИНИ ҶУРГАНИШДА ҚОН ЗАРДОБИ ПЕПСИНОГЕН ДАРАЖАСИНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ**Юсупова Н.А., Маннонова Н.Ў., Санаева П., Курбанова Ш.Б.**

Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети, Самарқанд ш., Ўзбекистон

Резюме. Ошқозон девори шиллиқ қаватини морфологик баҳолаш эндоскопия, биопсия ва гистологик текширув зарурати мавжудлиги туфайли жуда кўп меҳнат талаб қилади. Бундан ташқари, ҳаттоки бир нечта биопсия материаллари ҳам гастритнинг фокал, нотекис тарқалиши туфайли аниқ тасвирни бермайди. Сўнгги ўн йилликларда I ва II пепсиногенларнинг зардобдаги концентрациясини аниқлаш ошқозон шиллиқ қаватининг ҳолатини ноинвазив баҳолаш учун кенг шиллатилиб келинмоқда. Мақолада пепсиногенларнинг ошқозон девори ҳолатини баҳолашдаги аҳамияти ва турли генезли касалликларда ўзгаришлари ҳақида маълумотлар келтирилган.

Калит сўзлар: иммунофермент анализ, пепсиноген 1 (PGI), пепсиноген 2 (PGII), қон зардоб, ошқозон, ИФА

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ УРОВНЯ ПЕПСИНОГЕНА В СЫВОРОТКЕ КРОВИ В ИЗУЧЕНИИ МОРФОФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНОГО СОСТОЯНИЯ СТЕНКИ ЖЕЛУДКА**Юсупова Н.А., Маннонова Н.У., Санаева П., Курбанова Ш.Б.**

Самарқандский государственный медицинский университет, г. Самарқанд, Узбекистан

Резюме. Морфологическая оценка слизистой оболочки желудка чрезвычайно трудоемка из-за необходимости проведения эндоскопии, биопсии и гистологического исследования. Кроме того, даже несколько биопсий не дают четкой картины из-за очагового, неравномерного характера гастрита. В последние десятилетия определение концентрации пепсиногенов I и II в сыворотке крови используется для неинвазивной оценки состояния слизистой оболочки желудка. В статье представлена информация о значении пепсиногенов в оценке состояния стенки желудка и их изменениях при заболеваниях различного генеза.

Ключевые слова: иммуноферментный анализ, пепсиноген 1 (PGI), пепсиноген 2 (PGII), сыворотка крови, желудок, ИФА

e-mail: nargiza-yusupova-87@mail.ru, Manonovano@gmail.com

Gastric cancer (GC) is one of the most common malignant neoplasms. Despite the long-term systematic reduction in GC incidence and mortality, about 50,000 new cases of the disease are registered in Russia annually, which creates a complex medical and social problem [1]. In terms of GC incidence in the world, Russia, like other Eastern European countries, ranks 3rd after Japan and China [2]. In Russia, GC in both men and women is in 2nd or 3rd place among all malignant neoplasms. At the same time, unlike Japan, in Russia almost half of newly diagnosed GC cases (approximately 35–50% depending on the region) represent stage IV (inoperable) of this disease [1]. Chronic atrophic gastritis is considered a precursor to gastric cancer [3]. As detailed studies by P. Correa, the development of intestinal gastric cancer regularly proceeds through a series of successive discrete morphological stages: superficial gastritis, atrophic gastritis, small intestinal

metaplasia, colonic metaplasia, progressive dysplasia, and carcinoma in situ, ending with invasive cancer. This process usually covers a period of 20–30 years [4]. It has been established that in individuals with atrophic gastritis of the body of the stomach, the risk of developing gastric cancer is increased by 3–5 times compared to individuals with a normal, healthy stomach (normal mucosa — no inflammation, no atrophy, no *Helicobacter pylori*). In the case of severe atrophic gastritis limited to the antral section, the incidence of gastric cancer is 18 times higher than in healthy individuals. If atrophic changes are present both in the antrum and in the body of the stomach (pangastritis or multifocal atrophic gastritis), the risk increases by approximately 90 times [3]. An equally important problem is erosive and ulcerative lesions of the gastroduodenal mucosa (most often associated with *H. pylori* infection and/or taking non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and occurring against the background of increased secretion of hydrochloric acid), often complicated by bleeding. Morphological assessment of the gastric mucosa is extremely labor-intensive due to the need for endoscopy, biopsy and histological examination. In addition, even several biopsies do not provide a clear picture due to the focal, uneven nature of gastritis. In recent decades, determination of the concentration of pepsinogens I and II in the blood serum has been used for non-invasive assessment of the condition of the gastric mucosa. Pepsinogens are inactive protein precursors of pepsin, which are autocatalytically converted into it in the presence of hydrochloric acid in gastric juice. In the human body, two such proenzymes are synthesized: pepsinogen 1 (PG1) and pepsinogen 2 (PG2), which differ in their molecular structure and immunological properties. The optimal pH values at which pepsin is formed from them are also different: for PG1 it is 1.5–2.0, and for PG2 it is 4.5. Pepsinogen 1 is produced by the main cells of the glands of the fundus and body of the stomach, pepsinogen 2 is produced by the mucin-forming cells of the glands of all parts of the stomach, as well as by Brunner's glands in the proximal part of the duodenum. In healthy people, the amount of PG1 formed is more than three times higher than PG2. Both pepsinogens can be detected in gastric juice and in human blood; only PG1 is normally detected in urine. In the 1980s, the American gastroenterologist M. Samloff established that the concentration of pepsin proenzymes in the blood serum correlates with the level of peptic secretion of the stomach and, more importantly, with the severity of damage to the gastric mucosa (GM), which was confirmed morphologically [1]. Based on this and subsequent studies, serum pepsinogens began to be used to diagnose the state of the GM [2, 3]. It is known that the gastric mucosa, regardless of the mechanisms of its damage, can regenerate and restore its original structure. However, with the progression of the inflammatory process of the gastric mucosa, the damaged glands lose the ability to regenerate and are replaced, including by cells that produce mucus and metaplastic epithelium, i.e. atrophic gastritis develops. Chronic atrophic gastritis is a disease classified as a precancerous condition, which significantly increases the risk of developing gastric cancer (GC) [4]. The greatest danger in terms of developing GC is atrophic gastritis with reduced acid-forming function of the stomach (the incidence of cancer is up to 13%). Chronic atrophic gastritis is detected in 90% of patients with GC. Therefore, it is currently believed that timely diagnostics of GC atrophy should be the first step in identifying the risk of gastric cancer [5]. The difficulty in early diagnostics of atrophic gastritis is that at the initial stages it can develop asymptotically for a long time or have minor clinical manifestations. The main diagnostic method for this disease is endoscopic examination, which reveals signs characteristic of GC atrophy. The final diagnosis is established by conducting a morphological analysis of biopsy samples taken during endoscopy. Atrophic gastritis is confirmed if a patient's biopsy reveals a decrease in the number of specialized glandulocytes that provide the secretory function of the stomach, and their replacement with simpler cells, including those that produce mucus. However, with inflammation, the microscopic picture may change and be incorrectly assessed by the researcher. Therefore, the results of a gastrobiopsy may contribute to hyper- and hypodiagnosis of atrophic gastritis [6]. In recent years, a number of studies have been conducted in laboratories in a number of countries to replace screening diagnostics of atrophic gastritis using endoscopy with more effective non-invasive methods. As a result of this work, it was shown that as a biological marker establishing a final diagnosis, conducting additional studies. At present, a comprehensive analysis of pepsinogens is already widely used in laboratories in a number of countries for annual screening examination of individuals over 50 years of age, as well as testing of patients at risk for stomach cancer every six months. This group is recommended to include close relatives of patients with gastric cancer, patients suffering from dyspepsia, ulcerative and gastroesophageal reflux disease, as well as smoking men over 45 years of age and frequently ill elderly people [16]. In addition, a comprehensive study of pepsinogens can be used instead of gastroscopy to examine individuals for whom it is undesirable to conduct it due to chronic inflammatory processes of the respiratory tract and cardiovascular system. Important advantages of this laboratory method of analysis are that it is simple to perform, allows obtaining reliable information about the state of the gastric mucosa in just 1.5–2.0 hours, without damaging it, as is the case with endoscopy [17]. This makes it possible to examine patients as needed, i.e. promptly and often enough [7]. It has been established that with a normal state of the gastric mucosa, the concentration of

PG1 in the blood serum of residents of European countries varies within 40-130 $\mu\text{g} / \text{l}$ [8]. With atrophic gastritis, the secretion of hydrochloric acid is noticeably reduced and, as a consequence, the concentration of serum PG1 decreases to values less than 40 $\mu\text{g} / \text{l}$ [9]. The use of quantitative PG1 analysis for diagnosing atrophic gastritis (including its early asymptomatic form) has currently become widespread in many developed countries, and in Japan it has already been included in screening studies [10]. The sensitivity and specificity of this method are more than 90%, and the reliability of the results obtained is significantly higher than when using endoscopy and histology [11]. The results of PG1 determination in screening studies allow us to identify individuals with a high risk of developing gastric cancer (atrophic gastritis is a precancerous condition) from the cohort of subjects, and to single out patients at risk for duodenal ulcers (they are characterized by serum PG1 concentrations above 165 $\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$) [12]. Quantitative analysis of serum PG2, as well as determination of the PG1/PG2 concentration ratio, provide valuable additional information on the state of the gastric mucosa. It has been established that in healthy residents of Western European countries, the normal PG1 values in the blood serum do not exceed 2–15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$, and the PG1/PG2 ratio is greater than 3 [13]. Exceeding the upper limit of the serum PG2 norm is an indicator that the subject has gastric mucosa inflammation of any etiology [14]. It has been shown that the value of the ratio of PG1 and PG2 concentrations in the blood serum of less than 3 serves as an additional diagnostic factor confirming atrophic gastritis [15]. Using the results of determining PG1, PG2 and the PG1/PG2 ratio allows us to differentiate functional dyspepsia from serious organic gastropathology (both tumor and other etiologies).

Conclusion. Thus, the conducted studies show that domestic test systems for determining the concentration of pepsinogens I and II are not inferior to the standard accepted in the world. Moreover, taking into account adequate quality and significantly lower price (approximately 3-4 times), it is necessary to introduce the achievements of new technologies into the practice of medical institutions. This approach will allow identifying a significant portion of precancerous conditions among the population for their further thorough examination.

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